

Law Teaching Methods for Students – Practice at Nam Can Tho University in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: Society's demand for the quality of qualified human resources with legal knowledge is increasing, especially human resources who are good at expertise and proficient in skills. Along with that trend, Nam Can Tho University plays an important role in training and supplying high-quality human resources for the development of the country in general and the Mekong Delta region in particular. Based on researching the teaching methods of Law modules for students at Nam Can Tho University, Vietnam, this article has proposed many useful solutions to improve teaching methods to develop thinking and skills for students according to the University's policy and meet the requirements of society.

Keywords: Teaching Methods, Law Teaching, Law Students

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1. Introduction

The general trend of today's society not only sets new requirements for employees with high subject qualifications and knowledge of the law but also promotes the development of education, especially the education of the younger generation. Building high-quality human resources has become an urgent task to meet the increasing demands of the labor market. This not only requires individuals to constantly improve their professional knowledge and skills but also requires the education system to have strong reforms and innovative teaching methods to help students develop comprehensively in terms of thinking, skills, and ability to adapt to social changes. One of the basic orientations of educational innovation today is to shift from an academic education far from reality to an education that focuses on forming the capacity to act and promote the initiative and creativity of learners (Nguyen Phi Vu & Nguyen The Hao, 2018). In the face of that requirement, on 04/11/2013, General Secretary Nguyen Phu Trong signed and promulgated the Resolution of the 8th Conference of the 11th Central Committee (Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW). The Resolution has affirmed that the guiding viewpoint in the orientation of fundamental and comprehensive reform of education and training is: "The development of education and training is to improve people's knowledge, train human resources, and foster talents. Strongly shift the educational process from mainly equipping knowledge to comprehensively developing learners' capacities and qualities". (Đang Cong san Viet Nam, 2013)

To realize the view of improving the quality of education, it is necessary to have close coordination between teachers and learners. In particular, innovating teaching methods is a key factor, helping to avoid dryness and rigidity, and at the same time creating attraction and excitement for learners. The Faculty of Law of Nam Can Tho University is one of the pioneers in applying positive teaching methods. This not only helps students master professional knowledge but also comprehensively develops thinking skills, problem analysis, and practical application ability. In this article, the authors analyze the method of teaching Law modules to students from practice at Nam Can Tho University.

2. Teaching methods of Law modules at Nam Can Tho University

By 2024, Nam Can Tho University will have 42 full-time undergraduate training majors, of which Law is one of the majors that society, parents, and students are very interested in. This is evidenced by the number of Law students studying at the University is over 1500 students. This is quite a large number for a non-public university in the Mekong Delta region at the current stage. According to the orientation of the Party and the State, teaching to develop capacity and quality for students is a teaching method to promote the positivity and initiative of learners (Vu Van Ban & Bui Ngoc Quan, 2017). The 13th National Congress of the Party has indicated, "Synchronously building institutions and policies to effectively implement the policy of education and training is the leading national policy and the key driving force for national development. Continue to synchronously innovate the objectives, contents, programs, methods, and methods of education and training in the direction of modernity and international integration. There is a policy of breakthrough development and improvement of the quality of higher education". In particular, the role of teachers does not only stop at imparting knowledge but also organizes activities to help learners form and develop their qualities and capacities. This becomes more feasible and effective when applied to practical modules, especially at universities, including Nam Can Tho University. Practical modules require lecturers to create many experiential activities, helping students directly participate in the learning and training process. These activities not only help students master theory, but also provide opportunities for them to develop practical skills, critical thinking, and practical application (Trinh Van Bieu & Tran Thi Ngoc Ha, 2016).

Like the training program of other disciplines, the training program in Law at Nam Can Tho University is issued based on the Regulations of the Ministry of Education and Training. However, due to the characteristics of Law in the group of social sciences, the modules are often academic, heavy on theory, and students mainly study based on documents. Therefore, if lecturers do not apply the right teaching methods, these modules can easily become an "obsession" for students, especially first-year Law students, at universities in general and Nam Can Tho University in particular. The psychology of "depression" can arise when the learning content is presented in a dry and unattractive way. To overcome this situation, the innovation of teaching methods is the first measure to create interest and help students love and be proactive in learning. At the Faculty of Law of Nam Can Tho University, lecturers have applied an active, student-centered teaching method, ensuring smooth coordination between teaching and learning activities, specifically as follows:

Firstly, lecturers have actively integrated practical knowledge and enhanced interaction with students.

In each session, lecturers not only stop at communicating theory but also integrate practical situations, helping abstract concepts become closer and easier to understand for students. Thanks to regular interaction, and encouraging students to participate in exchanges and ask questions, lecturers not only help students master knowledge but also

create an exciting learning environment, and promote confidence and boldness when speaking in front of the group.

In addition, the lecturer also focuses on developing theoretical thinking for students by making judgments on the basic aspects of the module such as the origin, and nature of the state and law, along with legal case exercises derived from practice in daily life. Through practical case exercises, students have the opportunity to practice identifying the elements that constitute violations of the law and determining the legal responsibilities of violators. This helps students not only gain a deeper understanding of the theory but also gradually form and develop critical thinking, an important skill when studying law and practicing later.

Second, lecturers create conditions for students to practice teamwork skills.

There are many learning skills, of which teamwork skills are one of the most effective skills in learning and career development. Collaboration skills, or more specifically, teamwork skills, are not only a valuable quality but also especially important in modern society (Nguyen The Diem My, 2017). Teamwork will help students expand their thinking and understand a problem more deeply. Thanks to the abundance of opinions, students have the opportunity to acquire knowledge in a comprehensive and multi-dimensional way. At the same time, teamwork also provides opportunities for students to develop many other skills such as listening skills, emotional management skills, and conflict resolution skills when disagreements occur. These are essential skills not only in the learning environment but also in the professional practice later on.

During the learning process, students are encouraged to work in a group at the Electronic Library of Nam Can Tho University. The library was inaugurated in September 2017, is a modern learning space with an area of 3,188m² including 4 floors, equipped with a computer system, air-conditioned, along with many other facilities such as conference rooms, seminar rooms, study and relaxation areas, and areas dedicated to group study,... The Library's favorable facilities not only meet the needs of learning but also create an ideal environment for students to work in groups. Students can take advantage of a wide range of learning resources, including original textbooks, monographs, print journals, and digital documents, which effectively support students' learning. Moreover, the teachers in charge of the Library are always ready to guide students on how to make the most of data sources, making research and group study more effective. This is one of the highlights of Nam Can Tho University, which is positively recognized through surveys to assess the quality of educational institutions, affirming the important role of the library in supporting the teaching and learning activities of lecturers and students.

Thirdly, strengthen the support and exchange of connections between students of all courses.

Lecturers have built a group of Law students who are good at their profession and proficient in skills to support the lower students, contributing to creating a mutually supportive learning environment. This group of students was established to guide first-year students in preparing presentation content, supporting skills such as PowerPoint drafting, online presentation via the Canva application,... and other learning skills. This is not only an opportunity for Law students in general to practice organizational skills and communication skills... it is also an opportunity for Law students to share their learning experiences and inspire new Law students to study at the University.

After three years of implementing this model, the lecturer in charge has recorded initial successes. Although the scale is still small, the positive effect it brings is very obvious. First-year students, who have just undergone a transition from a traditional high school learning environment with traditional teaching methods to a university environment where

the learner is the center, often have difficulty adapting to new learning facilities and methods. At the same time, the lack of confidence and timidity when approaching lecturers is also a significant barrier.

The support from upper-class students who have studied Law will help first-year students be more confident in asking questions and solving problems. This group of students acts as a bridge, helping them confidently shake off the "safety cover" and put on the "coat" of confidence, ready to participate in the learning process more actively and effectively.

Fourthly, lecturers have "rewards" to encourage concentration, encourage critical thinking in theoretical lessons, and, at the same time take measures to promptly handle specific objects.

To increase the ability to concentrate on listening to lectures and improve the efficiency of knowledge acquisition, and at the same time limit frequent absences among students, lecturers have taken many creative and practical measures. One of those measures is to integrate into theoretical lessons words of encouragement, advice, and orientation for students on clearly defined learning goals. Lecturers encourage students to build a reasonable timetable between subjects, concentrate intensely during lectures, and limit absences from class so as not to interrupt the process of acquiring knowledge.

In addition, lecturers also apply the form of giving plus points to students who actively speak and interact with lecturers and other members of the class. This is an effective solution to help overcome passivity, timidity, and the psychology of "fear of being wrong" common in students. For students who are special, lack concentration, or cause disorder in the class, lecturers actively arrange seating positions at the first rows of tables to promptly support interaction and encourage students to contribute to building more positive lessons.

For these methods to be implemented effectively, the role of the leaders of the Faculty and the University in paying close attention and directing is extremely important. Lecturers are always aware of the importance of the State and Law Theory module and proactively improve their professional qualifications by coordinating with relevant organizations. Lecturers have cooperated with the National Political Publishing House – Can Tho Branch to place monographs and related textbooks, providing more knowledge and learning materials for students. At the same time, Nam Can Tho University also cooperates with the Electronic Library to place monographs for this module. Currently, the Library has more than 15 books on the field of State and Law, meeting the learning and research needs of students, and creating favorable conditions for both lecturers and students in improving the quality of teaching and learning.

3. Difficulties and solutions to innovate teaching methods of Law modules for students at Nam Can Tho University

In addition to the above achievements, the teaching of this module also faces some difficulties as follows:

First, the content of the module is abstract and extensive theory (Pham Thi Phuong, 2023), making students, especially first-year students, easily feel difficult to absorb and lack interest if there is no appropriate teaching method:

The Law modules contain abstract and complex concepts such as the origin, nature of the state, legal theories, or systemic issues related to the operating mechanism of the state apparatus. For first-year students, these contents can be strange and confusing,

because they do not have a solid legal knowledge foundation to approach and grasp the problem comprehensively. Moreover, the disparity between teaching methods at the high school level (mainly passive listening) and university learning methods (requiring initiative and criticism) can make it difficult for students to adapt. The abstraction of the module content can lead to boredom and a lack of motivation to learn if the lecturer does not know how to make the lecture lively and easy to understand. Students will feel heavy when they have to memorize dry theoretical concepts without seeing practical connections, thereby easily leading to a loss of interest, lack of concentration, and decreased academic performance.

Therefore, to avoid boredom and arouse students' passion and interest in learning, lecturers need to:

First, use active teaching methods and diversify teaching forms: Lecturers need to apply active, student-centered teaching methods such as group discussions, quick questions and answers, and presentations according to specific legal situations. Instead of only teaching theory traditionally, lecturers can integrate practical legal situations, regularly allow students to discuss, work in groups, give presentations in front of the collective, etc. This will help students better understand how to apply theoretical knowledge to practice, and at the same time arouse students' curiosity and interest in the subject content.

Second, simplify the content and illustrate it with specific examples: To solve abstract and complex problems, lecturers should divide the module content into smaller, more receptive parts. The use of specific examples, illustrations, or comparisons of legal concepts with real-life events will help students grasp the problem better. When seeing the practical application of theoretical knowledge, students will feel that knowledge becomes closer and more valuable.

Third, increase the use of technology in teaching: Lecturers can use technology tools such as PowerPoint and video slideshows to illustrate abstract content. Interactive lectures on online platforms or through educational apps such as Canva, Kahoot, or Quizizz will help students get more engaged and encourage them to actively participate in learning activities.

Fourth, provide case exercises for students to apply knowledge: An effective way to help students overcome the abstraction of the module content is to provide practical case exercises, which allow students to apply theory to solve specific problems. This not only helps students better understand concepts but also develops critical thinking skills and problem-solving skills – these are important skills that Law students need to have.

Fifth, create a space for discussion and student support: Lecturers need to build an open learning environment, encouraging students to ask questions and discuss. After-school discussions or academic advising sessions can be organized to answer questions, helping students master difficult knowledge. This timely support will help students reduce stress and feel overwhelmed by the large amount of knowledge.

Monday, the status of "vegetarian learning", "rote learning" and "vegetarian studies" is a worrying issue, especially for first-year students. Many students only memorize without really understanding the essence of the problem, leading to a lack of critical thinking skills and the ability to apply knowledge to practice. The main cause of this phenomenon is a lack of motivation and clear learning goals. Students often do not attach importance to achieving excellent academic results and just pass the subject without focusing on cultivating knowledge. In other words, students do not focus on understanding the root causes and problem residues and do not have the habit of reading and studying documents, some students rarely come to the library and use the learning materials in the

library to cultivate and expand their knowledge. The reason for this situation is that the consciousness of students, especially first-year students, has not changed (Do Van Hung, 2017). Overall student interest in reading has dropped alarmingly (Thu Hang, 2022), which can be explained by the strong development of the internet, the birth of social networks such as Facebook and Zalo, and the development of entertainment applications on mobile devices... The strong development of the internet, social networks, and entertainment applications such as Facebook and Zalo also contributes greatly to reducing students' interest in reading and researching. With a wide range of entertainment information and online facilities, students are easily attracted and spend time on less academic activities. This leads to students spending less time on self-study, especially going to the Library to study and use academic materials. Although the University's e-Library provides an extensive system of learning materials, students do not make effective use of these resources.

The solution proposed to overcome the above difficulties is that the Faculty of Law in particular and the Faculties in general need to implement the following contents:

First, encourage the use of the Library through the addition of training points: One of the practical solutions to motivate students to come to the Library is to apply the form of adding training points for students who regularly exploit learning materials at the Library. The Faculty of Law in particular and other faculties in the university in general need to closely coordinate with the Department of Student Management to study and propose this point accrual mechanism. This will motivate students not only to come to the Library but also to help them form a habit of using academic resources to improve their knowledge.

Second, integrate content to encourage reading into class activities: Academic advisors need to integrate content to encourage students to read books and study materials in monthly class activities. This is not just a reminder, but also a need for specific activities such as organizing contests or discussions related to law books and monographs that students have studied. This not only helps students create a habit of reading but also creates a space for sharing and discussion for students to learn and exchange knowledge.

Third, strengthen extracurricular activities related to academic research: The University can organize seminars, seminars, or legal knowledge competitions, encourage students to participate, and present the researched content from the materials at the library. These activities allow students to apply theoretical knowledge to practice, and at the same time create motivation for self-study and reading.

Fourth, integrate technology and build a more attractive e-library: To adapt to the trend of technological development, the University should focus on developing an e-library system with a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface, providing more digitized materials such as lecture videos, etc., and online learning materials. This will help students access knowledge more flexibly and conveniently, especially for students who are working part-time jobs and do not have time to go to the library in person.

Fifth, build a positive learning environment and encourage students to set clear learning goals: To overcome the lack of learning goals, academic advisors need to guide students in setting specific learning goals, not only in terms of grades but also in terms of developing skills and knowledge. Creating counseling sessions, sharing learning experiences, and career orientation can help students realize the true value of learning and thereby change their consciousness and be more positive in the learning process.

Tuesday on how to organize the class: One of the major challenges in teaching the Law modules at Nam Can Tho University is the large number of classes, up to about 120

students/class. The organization of classes on such a large scale makes it difficult to manage the classroom, the interaction between lecturers and students is limited, and at the same time negatively affects the ability of students to absorb knowledge. When the number of students is too large, it is difficult for lecturers to closely monitor each individual, thereby not being able to effectively apply modern teaching methods, especially interactive and student-centered teaching methods. In addition, the large number of classes makes students lack the opportunity to practice and participate in group discussion activities, thereby affecting the process of forming and developing students' legal thinking. Especially for subjects with an extensive theoretical nature and requiring analysis, the large number of classes makes students feel more pressure and difficult to absorb. (Diep Phuong Chi, 2015)

To overcome the above difficulties in the current context, it is necessary to:

First, separating class sections and reducing the number of students: To improve the quality of teaching and learning, the separation of class sections is a necessary solution. The Faculty of Law is proposing to reduce the number to 60 students/class. This will make it easier for lecturers to manage classes, track the progress of each student, and create better conditions for students to participate in discussions, Q&A, and interact directly with lecturers.

Second, take advantage of modern facilities: Nam Can Tho University has been continuously investing in modern facilities, including comfortable classrooms and an e-library with full learning materials. By separating classes with smaller numbers, we can make more effective use of modern classrooms, create comfortable learning spaces, meet students' interaction needs, and develop skills. This helps to improve teaching efficiency and encourages students to actively participate in the learning process.

Third, apply active teaching methods: With smaller classes, lecturers can flexibly apply positive teaching methods such as project-based learning, group discussions, small group work and practice practical situations. These methods not only help students acquire knowledge actively but also develop soft skills such as critical thinking, communication skills, problem-solving, and teamwork.

Fourth, strengthen the interaction between lecturers and students: When classes are held in small numbers, lecturers have more time to interact directly with students, supporting students in times when they encounter difficulties in the learning process. This also helps lecturers easily adjust teaching methods to suit the receptivity of each student.

Fifth, strengthen monitoring and evaluation of the learning process: With the right number of classes, lecturers can implement a continuous assessment system, not only based on final exam results but also through activities such as discussions, group exercises, and presentations, helping students understand knowledge in depth instead of just learning to cope.

Fourthly, the model of a group of Law students who are good at their profession and proficient in guiding students in the lower course has brought many positive results, helping first-year students quickly adapt to the new learning environment and improve their learning and presentation skills. However, this model is still seasonal, only supported in the 1st semester of each year – when this module is taught. This makes the group's activities not maintained regularly, reducing the effectiveness of supporting students in other modules. In addition, the maintenance of the group's operations is now largely based on personal funding, making it difficult to organize larger-scale or long-term activities. Therefore, to effectively replicate and exploit this model in the coming time, it is necessary to implement:

First, develop a long-term operating regulation: To ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the model, the Faculty of Law needs to propose the University to develop an official regulation for a group of students who are good at their profession and proficient in skills, helping to maintain operations throughout the academic year, not limited to the 1st semester. This regulation can stipulate the rights and obligations of members, the organizational process, and the criteria for participation, ensuring that the group can support students in many different modules.

Second, upgrade the model to a Law Student Club: Upgrading the group to a Law Student Club with good expertise and skills can help expand the scope of activities. The club can organize skills tutorials, seminars, and forums to share learning experiences, not only for Law students but also for students from other disciplines within the University. This will help students develop more comprehensively in terms of knowledge and skills and, at the same time, create conditions for students in the upper and lower courses to study, exchange, and support each other.

Third, proposing financial support from the University: For the model to operate sustainably, financial support from the University is needed. Schools should consider funding groups or clubs, making it possible for them to organize activities more regularly without relying on individual resources. This funding can be used to organize group study sessions and workshops, purchase learning materials, or organize competitions to encourage student participation.

Fourth, develop a student-based academic mentoring system: One of the ways to make this model more effective is to create an academic mentoring system where students with good expertise and skills can act as mentors to junior students throughout their studies. This mentorship system can include supporting students in various modules, helping them build a streamlined learning pathway, sharing learning methods, and even career orientation support.

Fifth, strengthen promotion and encourage participation: For this model to develop and attract more students' participation, it is necessary to have stronger promotion through the University's information channels such as websites, message boards, and social networks. At the same time, there should be policies to encourage and recognize the student's contribution to this group or Club, such as accumulating training points or certification of participation in extracurricular activities.

4. Conclusion

In the context of modern society, the demand for high-quality human resources is increasing, requiring educational institutions to constantly improve teaching methods and organize classes to meet this requirement. Nam Can Tho University, especially the Faculty of Law, has made efforts to innovate the teaching method of Law modules towards developing thinking and skills for students. Solutions such as integrating practical knowledge, encouraging teamwork, and building a group of students to support the lower course have all proven effective in improving the quality of training. We do not deny the role of traditional teaching methods, but need to combine more positive teaching methods - this is very necessary to improve the quality of teaching and learning at Nam Can Tho University in the current period.

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